

KEY FACTORS IN THE STUDY OF RUSSIAN LITERATURE

Yuldasheva Sabina Yusufovna

Teacher at Kokand State Pedagogical Institute

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Abstract: The article examines Russian literature as one of the factors of self-knowledge and self-development, the world around us is also examined through the prism of the concept of Russian literature and the history of its development.

Key words: Russian literature; critic; visual media; cultural revolution; literary resolution Russian literature, aspects of development, historical division of literature, periodization of Russian literature, writers.

Literature in general is one of the ways to understand the world, humanity, and oneself. Literature conveys the thoughts, views of the author, his attitude to life and reality in the best possible way. And each writer creates his own artistic world, with which one or another reader will agree and accept it. The painter also draws pictures of life and images. The lives and characters of people are reflected in music, sculpture and literature.

The writer's weapon is the word. Fiction is the art of words. Contact with the world of art gives us joy and selfless pleasure. Many therefore see the works of writers, composers, and artists as a means of pleasant pastime. Of course, we often go to the cinema, sit down in front of the TV or computer to relax, or even have fun. And the artists, composers, programmers, writers themselves, knowing the laws of art, structure their works in such a way as to excite, support and develop the interest and even curiosity of viewers and listeners. But the meaning of art in human life is incomparably more serious and richer.

No art can depict a person so clearly and “three-dimensionally” as painting and sculpture. But both the painter and the sculptor “capture” only one moment of life, and, looking at a painting and sculpture, we only guess about what preceded this moment and what will follow it. Neither the painter nor the sculptor has the means to show their heroes in movement, in change, in development. This can be done by the art of cinema, which wonderfully fuses the features of the art of speech, stage art, painting, music, artistic photography and computer graphics. But let's not forget that feature films are created on the basis of literary scripts. It is impossible to translate lyrical works into the “language” of cinema.

With all the immense power of cinematography, there are areas of social and inner life of a person that are accessible only to the art of words. A writer can draw one moment and the story of a human life. And one event, and a chain of the most complex events.

Changes associated with the progress of science and technology lead to a change in the current generation of previous ideals and assessments, and the search for new criteria. We are talking about the material and the spiritual, but separating one from the other is not so easy. Every powerful rise of literary thought that influenced the upbringing of the younger generation always carries with it an element of spirituality. Higher technical and creative capabilities affect the way of thinking and life of young people. But this does not mean at all that young people should reject the highest spiritual and cultural values, and they should not make them dependent on material wealth. There is such a thing as the culture of a people, which is rooted deep in the national soil and history. At all times, creators of verbal art in their works truthfully and fully reflect the complexity and diversity of human life and society, vividly and

intelligibly express their thoughts about the meaning of life, their innermost feelings. The moral position of the author unobtrusively influences the reader, who, while enjoying the word, getting to know amazing characters, gets to know the world and develops high civic feelings in himself. The concept of “formation” in pedagogy covers in its content a range of external (social, economic, educational, etc.) and internal (independent activity of the individual, self-education, etc.) factors that are inextricably interconnected and ensure the formation and development of the individual. Based on this position that the successful formation of moral values is ensured by a set of external and internal conditions that contribute to their formation. It follows that, along with the educational activities of the teacher, self-educational activities of students are necessary to master the moral values of future philologists. Based on the provisions of the personality-oriented approach, that students’ self-education activities ensure that they are placed in the position of subjects of the process of formation of moral values and contribute to the manifestation of maximum activity and independence in their development of moral values. Artistic creations of A. S. Pushkin, M. Yu. Lermontov, N. V. Gogol, L. N. Tolstoy, F. M. Dostoevsky, A. P. Chekhov, M. Sholokhov — allow the younger generation not only to recognize the past, but also to experience together with their heroes, to form views, feelings, character, awaken a love for beauty, and cultivate readiness to fight for the triumph of goodness and truth.

Various authors offer different options for periodizing the history of Russian literature. The encyclopedic dictionary of Brockhaus and Efron, published at the end of the 19th century, identified three periods in the history of Russian literature: from the first monuments to the Mongol-Tatar yoke, from the Mongol-Tatar yoke until the end of the 17th century, and from the 18th century until the time of publication of the dictionary (that is, until the end of the 19th century). D. P. SvyatopolkMirsky, who published a two-volume work on the history of Russian literature in London in 1927, identified the following periods in it: Old Russian (XI-XVII centuries), transitional, the period of classicism, the golden age of poetry, the era of Gogol, the period of realism and modern his period from 1881 (after the death of F. M. Dostoevsky). Published around the same time in the USSR, The Literary Encyclopedia divided the periods of Russian literature into the following stages: Old Russian literature, literature of the 18th century, literature of the 19th century, literature of the 20th century before the October Revolution, and literature of the 20th century after the October Revolution. The Literary Encyclopedia divided the periods of Russian literature into the following stages: Old Russian literature, literature of the 18th century, literature of the 19th century, literature of the 20th century before the October Revolution, and literature of the 20th century after the October Revolution. Literature fosters a sense of beauty and enriches a person’s spiritual world. The subject of depiction of literature is most often people of a specific historical era, their thoughts, feelings, relationships with each other, their life ideals - in a word, the inner and spiritual world of a person. Fiction, like science, has enormous educational power. It promotes the spread of education and culture among the younger generation. Whatever writers and poets talk about in their works, they think about the reader, about the person. Therefore, M. Gorky very accurately noted that literature is the study of humanity.

The power of fiction lies primarily in its aesthetic impact. This is the art that activates human spiritual forces: mind, intuition, feelings, aesthetic concepts. Aesthetic education is the cultivation in people of the ability and need to see, understand and appreciate beauty in all its manifestations and bring it into life, the ability to understand the sublime, tragic, comic. The

complex and delicate task of aesthetic education of the younger generation is solved through the joint efforts of family, school, and the public. Young people are educated aesthetically on the vast historical experience of writers.

Aesthetic emotions evoked by a work of art contribute to the perception of social ideas not only by the mind, but also by the heart, and awaken an active attitude towards the life pictures drawn in the work. Literature ensures the centuries-old continuity of culture and its increasing universality.

By creating universally significant ideas - images that grow into universal human symbols, it expresses the meaning of all historical development. Hamlet, Don Quixote, Prince Myshkin, the Master and Margarita are no longer just artistic images - they are symbols of culturally significant universal values.

Reading works like "Crime and Punishment", "War and Peace", "Anna Karenina", "Garnet Bracelet", young people change, their attitude to life changes, and they become better people. The works touch them to the depths of their hearts and educate them. Fiction is accessible to everyone, but the depth of its understanding depends on whether the student knows how to read it and what kind of student he is, his tastes and interests, and moral and ideological attitudes.

References:

1. Балатукова, З. И. Роль художественной литературы в воспитании молодого поколения / З. И. Балатукова. — Текст: непосредственный // Молодой ученый. — 2015. — № 15 (95). — С. 661-663. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/95/21305/> (дата обращения: 22.12.2021)
2. Акишина, А. А. Жесты и мимика в русской речи. Лингвострановедческий словарь / А.А. Акишина, Х. Кано, Т.К. Акишина. – М.: Русский язык, 1991. С. 145
3. Большой академический словарь русского языка. Т. 18: Подлещ – Порой. М; СПб: Наука, 2011. С. 772
4. Виноградов В.В. Очерки по истории русского литературного языка XVII–XIX вв. – М.: Высшая Школа, 2008. – 332 с.
5. Демьянов В.Г. Иноязычная лексика в истории русского языка XI–XVII веков. Проблемы морфологической адаптации. – М.: Наука, 2001. – 278 с.
6. Ковалевская Е.Г. История русского литературного языка. – М.: Просвещение, 1992. – 324 с.
7. Соболевский А.И. История русского литературного языка. – Уфа: Языки славянской культуры, 2006. – 298 с.